

Electron transfer reactions involving organic molecules[†]

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The problem, in studying the mechanism of an oxidation-reduction reaction is to find out whether atom/group or electron transfer has occurred, which atoms are transferred or how many electrons are transferred and what intermediates stable or unstable are formed? A complete study would include a detailed understanding of the transition state of all the steps involved. For obtaining such information kinetic measurements are very useful¹⁻⁶.

Many transition and non-transition metal ions act as good oxidants in acidic, basic or neutral medium. Generally, redox reactions are classified as one or two equivalent ones depending upon the number of electrons transferred. Higginson and Marshall⁷ suggested the following empirical rules for categorizing one and two equivalent oxidants irrespective of whether the reactions belong to atom or direct electron transfer category.

(a) Species derived from transition elements react with each other by a series of univalent changes,

(b) Species derived from non-transitional elements react with each other in a series of bivalent changes unless at least one of the reactants is a free radical, in which case univalent change is possible,

(c) Species derived from a transition element and a non-transition element react with each other by either univalent or bivalent changes, univalent changes being more common.

(in two one-equivalent steps)

One of the consequences of these rules is that the intermediates exhibit unusual oxidation states. Shaffer's principle of equivalence change⁸ envisages that non-complementary reactions between one-equivalent reductants and two-equivalent oxidants (or vice versa) are often slow compared to complementary reactions in which both oxidant and reductant change their oxidation state by the same number. The principle is based on (i) low probability of ter-

molecular mechanism, and (ii) formation of unstable oxidation states in case of non-complementary reactions.

Oxidants in redox process exist in several stable and/or unstable oxidation states. These are classified as one and two equivalent oxidants and are listed in Table 1.

Table 1

One-equivalent oxidants	Two-equivalent oxidants
$\text{Co}^{\text{III}}/\text{Co}^{\text{II}}$	$\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}/\text{Tl}^{\text{I}}$
$\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}/\text{Mn}^{\text{I}}$	$\text{Pb}^{\text{IV}}/\text{Pb}^{\text{II}}$
$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}} : \text{Cu}^{\text{III}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$	$\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}/\text{Pd}^{\text{0}}$
$\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}/\text{Ce}^{\text{II}}$	$\text{Mg}^{\text{II}}/\text{Mg}^{\text{0}}$
$\text{Ag}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ag}^{\text{I}}$	$\text{Hg}^{\text{II}}/\text{Hg}^{\text{0}}$
$\text{Ir}^{\text{IV}}/\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}$	$\text{Au}^{\text{III}}/\text{Au}^{\text{I}}$
$\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}$	$\text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}/\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}$
$\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}/\text{Cr}^{\text{II}}$	$\text{I}^{\text{V}}/\text{I}^{\text{V}}$
$\text{W}^{\text{VI}}/\text{W}^{\text{V}}$	

All the redox couples in the two-equivalent oxidants (column in Table 1) have been shown to pass through intermediate oxidation state of low stability⁹. Thus the Michael's postulate that the oxidation of organic compounds involving two-electron transfer follows two one-equivalent steps appears to be still valid, so long as the mechanism of electron transfer is by outer-sphere type. For example Tl^{II} has been detected by pulse radiolysis as well as by flash photolysis technique, although Tl^{III} undergoes fast disproportionation to Tl^{I} ($k = 2.3 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\Delta G = -62.7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S = -63 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$). Some reagents such as Cr^{VI} , Mn^{VII} , Pt^{IV} , V^{V} etc. act as both one- and two-equivalent oxidants depending on the conditions employed. One-equivalent oxidants are highly unstable in neutral solution and can be stabilized by the addition of acid or alkali. When one- and two-equivalent oxidants of similar redox potential are compared, it is observed that the latter react much faster than one-equivalent oxidants, probably because during the two-electron transfer reaction high energy free radicals are not formed and there is overall twice the free energy change.

It is possible to distinguish one- and two-equivalent paths kinetically from product analysis and stoichiometry of certain reactions.

(1) One-equivalent oxidants tend to convert sulfite (SO_3^{2-}) to dithionate ($\text{S}_2\text{O}_6^{2-}$), while two-equivalent oxidants

[†]Prof. G. V. Bakore Memorial Lecture (1999) delivered under the auspices of Indian Chemical Society on November 17, 2000 at Hardwar.

tend to produce sulfate (SO_4^{2-}),

(2) One-equivalent oxidants generally tend to convert hydrazine (N_2H_4) to ammonia (NH_3) and nitrogen, while two-equivalent oxidants tend to convert hydrazine (N_2H_4) to ammonia and hydrazoic acid (HN_3),

(3) Cyclobutanol exhibits high reactivity¹⁰ towards one-equivalent oxidants and reacts with C–C bond cleavage yielding open-chain products, while with two-equivalent reagents it does not react particularly fast and proceeds by a C–H bond cleavage yielding cyclobutanone.

(4) Esters, during oxidation produce CO_2 and other products with one equivalent oxidant while with two equivalent oxidants, oxidation occurs without evolution of CO_2 . In the case of oxidation by the one equivalent oxidants six moles of oxidant is consumed for each mole of ester, whereas with two equivalent oxidants one mole of oxidant is consumed for every mole of ester¹¹.

(5) In one equivalent redox reactions the reaction rate is affected by the addition of vinyl monomers or HgCl_2 or presence of oxygen but no such thing happens with two equivalent oxidants.

Oxidants involving metal ions can also be classified based on whether the transfer of electrons involves coordination sphere or ionic sphere of the metal ions.

Outer-sphere reactions :

In the outer-sphere reactions, the metal ion retains its full coordination shell and there is a direct electron transfer from the reducing agent to the oxidant. In these reactions the ligand exchange or displacement is slower than electron transfer. An example of this type of reaction is

where both the reactants are inert complexes. Other examples include reactions between bipyridyl complexes of Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} , hexacyano complexes of Mn^{III} and Mn^{II} , hexacyano complexes of Fe^{III} and Fe^{II} and MnO_4^- and MnO_3^- .

Inner-sphere reactions :

In reactions, which follow inner-sphere mechanism the transfer of electrons is preceded by the displacement of ligands of oxidant by reductant. In this case ligand displacement is faster than electron transfer process. A typical example of a redox process, which proceeds via inner-sphere mechanism, is the oxidation of Cr^{2+} to CrCl^{2+} by ruthenium(III) complex,

The evidence for this inner-sphere mechanism comes from the detection of the following intermediate during a spectroscopic study³,

The formation of this intermediate and electron transfer are relatively rapid³ so that this intermediate spends most of its life-time in the $\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}-\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}$ form and the dissociation of this is rate-determining.

Most of the oxidation reactions fit into one of the following categories : (i) electron transfer reactions, (ii) proton transfer reactions, (iii) hydride ion transfer reactions, (iv) hydrogen atom transfer reactions, and (v) oxygen or chlorine atom transfer reactions.

Electron transfer reactions :

For redox reactions in gaseous systems direct electron transfer between molecules is possible¹². The situation in liquid systems is complicated and the transfer of electron/s between two particles is hindered by the presence of solvent molecules, which prevent the extension into space of the orbital of the exchanging particles. Hence atom or group transfer reactions are considered more likely in such solutions. Electron transfer is said to occur when an electron is physically transferred between two dissimilar species. The transfer of a hydrogen atom is equivalent to the transfer of one electron and that of a hydride ion is equivalent to the transfer of two electrons.

The Frank-Condon principle^{8,13} states that the nuclear motion is slow ($>10^{-13}$ s) compared to the electron motion ($\approx 10^{-15}$ s). This means that the nuclei remain frozen in position during the act of electron transfer. In complex ions, the ligands act as good insulating groups for the electrons and orbitals of the central metal ion. In addition, the ligands are bound to the exchanging particles in a non-identical manner. For example, in the following electron exchange reaction,

the iron-oxygen bond distances in the Fe^{III} ions are shorter than those in the Fe^{II} ions. As per the Frank-Condon principle, in the normal state of these complexes, the transfer of an electron would result in an Fe^{III} ion with elongated bonds and an Fe^{II} ion with shortened bonds. Since the products of electron exchange would then have a higher energy than the reactants, the possibility of the exchange should be very small. Exchange can occur easily only when the two particles have nearly identical structure and configuration.

Except for the transferring electron, it is also important that the two ions have identical spin states. If by electron exchange there is an overall change in the spin, the transition is quantum mechanically forbidden and can proceed only very slowly. For example, exchange is slow between amine complexes of Co^{II} and Co^{III} because Co^{III} is spin-paired while Co^{II} has three unpaired electrons.

Ligands that can act as bridging groups also facilitate electron transfer between two metal ions because these bridging groups bind them in the activated complex and the electron can pass through this complex with ease. Some examples of bridging ligands are H_2O , OH^- , O^{2-} , F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , N_3^- , SCN^- and CO_2^- . In some cases these ligands can also act as electron conduction media by allowing the electron to move from one end of the ligand in first coordination sphere to the other end where the second coordination sphere starts.

Proton transfer reactions :

An example of an oxidation reaction in which the rate-determining step is proton abstraction, is the carbonyl elimination reaction which benzylnitrates undergo, under the influence of a base to produce benzaldehyde and nitrite ion. The mechanism proposed by Baker and Heggs⁴ is

The Hammett's reaction constant ρ for this reaction is +3.4 as expected. In a particular reaction series it is possible to know whether the reaction proceeds via a proton transfer or not from a study of substituent effects on isotope effect. The isotope effect $k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$ is strongly affected by the introduction of electron-releasing or -withdrawing substituents in a reaction series, if the hydrogen is transferred as a proton. An isotope effect almost independent of the substituents indicates a hydride ion transfer. Use of this criterion led Swain *et al.*⁵ to choose a mechanism from among the following alternatives for the decarboxylation of β -ketoacids in benzene :

Kinetic isotope effects $k_{\text{COOH}}/k_{\text{COOD}}$ in the decarboxylation of substituted benzoylacetic acids in benzene at 50° as reported by Swain *et al.*⁶ were found to be dependent on the type of substituent present. They are 2.8 for *m*-nitro, 1.7 for unsubstituted, and 0.85 for *p*-methyl, though these substituents have negligible effect on O-H frequencies in the ground state. Such a variation of isotope effect with substituents, shows that the reaction proceeds via proton transfer mechanism-I.

Hydride ion transfer mechanism :

Several reactions, which proceed by hydride ion transfer mechanism, are known in literature. These include oxidation of alcohols¹⁴, Sommelet conversion of primary alkyl halides to aldehydes^{15,16}, reduction of enamines by formic acid¹⁷, Leuckart reduction of ketones by ammonium formate¹⁸ and hydrolysis of pyridine diaryl boranes¹⁹. The mechanism of dehydrogenation of aromatic compounds by tetrachloro-1,2 benzoquinone has been studied by Jackman and Thompson²⁰. The rate of this reaction was found to be well correlated with Hammett substituent constant σ^* for the group Z. The mechanism proposed is as follows :

The correlation of rate with σ^* and the sign and magnitude of the reaction constant ρ (-2.5) suggests that the rate-controlling step involves hydride ion transfer. In the oxidation of alcohols by bromine, two mechanisms have been proposed to explain all kinetic and other data observed experimentally :

In step-1 the cleavage of the C-H bond is shown via a hydride ion with simultaneous transfer of the hydrogen from the O-H group as proton. On the contrary, step-2 envisages cleavage of the C-H bond via proton transfer with simultaneous transfer of the O-H hydrogen atom as a hydride ion. Neither the kinetic equation, isotope effect on a single alcohol, nor the effect of substituents (Z) on the overall rate

could distinguish the two mechanisms. Swain suggested that an isotope effect $k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$ independent of substituents in a reaction series indicates hydride transfer. Hence, determining the effect of substituents on the isotope effect of each of the hydrogens, i.e. the alcoholic hydrogen and the hydrogen attached to the carbon (taking part in the reaction), one at a time was applied to permit such a distinction. It was found that the C-H isotope effect does not get affected by substituting the methyl hydrogens ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$ for Z=H was 2.94 and Z=F 2.83). This insensitivity of isotope effect to substitution shows that the C-H hydrogen is transferred as hydride ion. On the contrary, the O-H isotope effect rises considerably with fluorine (1.49 for Z=H to 2.06 for Z=F) suggesting O-H hydrogen to be involved in a proton transfer process. This shows that the oxidation of alcohols by bromine proceeds via mechanism-1. Thus a study of the effect of substituents on isotopic effect helps a long way in understanding reaction mechanisms.

Hydrogen atom transfer reactions :

Permanganate oxidation of alcohols²¹, fluorhydrates²² and formic acid²³⁻²⁶ proceeds by a hydrogen atom abstraction from the anions of these molecules. For example, the mechanism for the oxidation of alcohols by permanganate is as follows.

The observed isotope effect for the above reaction was unusually large being 16.1. Hydrogen atom abstraction from the α -position of alcohols can occur not only when it reacts with permanganate, but also with any reactive reagent such as H-atom,

This reaction also exhibits an unusually large isotope effect $k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 17$. Unlike the proton or hydride ion transfer reac-

tions, the hydrogen atom transfer reactions are accompanied by very large isotope effects. These reactions also differ from the proton and hydride transfer reactions with respect to Hammett's rho value. For most of the hydrogen atom abstraction reactions Hammett's rho is very small (< 0.1).

Table 2 gives the characteristics of H⁺, H⁻ and H atom transfer reactions.

Table 2			
	Proton transfer	Hydrogen atom transfer	Hydride ion
Isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$)	Small	Moderate	Fairly high
Effect of substituents on value the $k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$	High	Not reported	Negligibly small
Sign of ρ or ρ^*	Positive	Negative	Negative
Magnitude of ρ or ρ^*	Very large	Very small	Very large

Oxygen or chlorine atom transfer reactions :

Certain redox reactions are known to proceed by transfer of atom other than hydrogen in the rate-determining step. A well-known oxygen atom transfer reaction is hypochlorite oxidation of nitrite ion. Taube²⁷ proposed the following mechanism for this reaction,

The activated complex in this case cleaves to produce nitrate and chloride ions.

Effect of multiple substituents on rates of reactions :

For studying the effect of structure on rates of reactions of organic compounds, a number of empirical models have been developed and the most successful and intensely investigated are the linear free energy relationships of which the Hammett's equation^{28,29} for aromatic and Taft's equation^{30,31} for aliphatic compounds in many reactions like oxidation, hydrolysis, condensation etc. have been successfully applied,

$$\log K = \log K^0 + \rho \sigma \quad (1)$$

$$\log k = \log k^0 + \rho \sigma \quad (2)$$

where K and k are equilibrium and rate constants respectively of a substituted compound, while K^0 and k^0 are the corresponding equilibrium and rate constants of the unsubstituted compound. The empirical constant sigma (σ) is known as substituent constant and measures the polar effect of the substituent in the *meta*- or *para*-position from the reaction centre and in principle, is independent of the reaction being studied. The other constant rho (ρ) known as

reaction constant, depends on the nature of the reaction and measures the susceptibility of the reaction to polar effects. The value of ρ depends not only on the nature of the reaction but also on the conditions employed such as solvent, temperature etc. It also indicates the amount of charge developed in the transition state during the course of the reaction. More the charge developed, larger is the magnitude of the ρ value and vice versa. The ρ value is usually determined from the slope of the linear plot of $\log K$ or $\log k$ versus σ or its modified versions like σ^+ and/or σ^- depending on the nature of the reaction (σ^+ for electron-releasing groups³² and σ^- for electron-withdrawing groups^{31,32}). The sign and magnitude of ρ gives useful information about the nature of the transition state and therefore can be used as a diagnostic tool in a reaction. For example, a negative ρ value indicates development of positive charge (or disappearance of negative charge) at the reaction centre during the formation of the transition state in the rate-determining step of the overall reaction while a positive value for ρ indicates development of a negative charge (or disappearance of positive charge) at the reaction centre. For an equilibrium process ρ is given by the difference in the ρ values for forward and backward reactions and can be positive or negative depending on the direction in which the reaction proceeds. Of the factors that control the absolute value of ρ , the distance (d) from the reaction centre is of utmost importance, more exactly it depends on the length and nature of the side-chain. When CH_2 group extends the side-chain the ρ value decreases. For example, ρ values for benzoic acid, phenyl acetic acid and phenyl propionic acid are 1.00, 0.49 and 0.21 which are in the decreasing order.

The extent of decrease is defined in terms of a factor called transmission factor π_y ,

$$\pi_y = \rho_{yz}/\rho_z \quad (3)$$

where ρ_{yz} is the reaction constant for the compound of the type Ar-Y-Z while ρ_z is the reaction constant for the compound of the type Ar-Z.

The value of the π_y indicates the ability of the chain to transmit polar effects^{33,36}. However, in order to obtain the general validity, π_y must be independent of the reaction centre chosen (Z), as long as the intervening group (Y) is the same in different reactions,

$$\rho_{yz}/\rho_z = \rho_{yz'}/\rho_{z'} \quad (4)$$

The so-called ρ - ρ relation (equation 4) has been shown to

hold good in many reactions like dissociation of carboxylic acids, reactions of carboxylic acids with diazophenylmethane, hydrolysis of their esters³⁴⁻³⁸ etc. For the insertion of a CH_2 group in Ar-Z, π_y corresponds to a value of about 0.4 (Refs. 39, 40) and with two CH_2 groups it decreases to approximately 0.2 (Refs. 36, 38, 40). Conjugated chains transmit the polar effects much better than saturated ones. A $>\text{CH}=\text{CH}<$ group is approximately equivalent to having one CH_2 group^{33,35,41,42}

Effect of solvent and temperature on ρ

Varying the dielectric constant of the medium affects the magnitude of ρ value. If the transition state is more polar than reactants, the increase in polarity of the solvent stabilizes the transition state, thus increasing the rate and this decreases the sensitivity of the reaction to the presence of substituents, resulting in a decrease of the ρ value. On the other hand, if the transition state is less polar or neutral, then change in dielectric constant of the medium may not have much effect.

The ρ values generally vary with temperature. For many reaction series, which follow the Hammett's equation, the entropy of activation is essentially constant^{28,43}. If that is so, ρ is expected to be inversely related to the absolute temperature. The variation of ρ with temperature is given by the equation,

$$\rho = \frac{\Delta H_o^\ddagger - \Delta H^\ddagger}{2.303 RT\sigma} \quad (5)$$

where ρ is proportional to $1/T$. Such a trend has been observed in many isoentropic reactions. There are also many reactions which are well-correlated by Hammett's equation and which have variable ΔS^\ddagger . In such cases a plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger is found to be linear. For such reactions the absolute magnitude of ρ decreases with temperature and becomes zero at what is called isokinetic temperature. Above this temperature the sign of ρ is reversed and its value then increases with increases in temperature⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶

Hammett's equation applies to reactions of compounds having a single substituent in benzene ring attached to the reacting side-chain. Extensions to certain more complicated types of compounds have been carried out later by several authors.

Modified Hammett's equation-exalted σ values :

When there is direct conjugation between the substituent and the reaction centre, the $\log k$ value corresponding to Hammett's σ value does not fall on line. Higher value of σ have to be used for fitting all the points on the line. These values are called exalted σ values and are denoted by σ^+ or

σ^- . σ^+ values are used for electron-donating substituents in *para*-position. The modified equation,

$$\log k/k^0 = \rho \sigma^+ \quad (6)$$

has been proposed by Okamoto and Brown³². σ^- values are used for electron-withdrawing substituents in *para*-position. If σ^- values are used in the above equation it is termed as Taft's equation^{30,31}. Charlton⁴⁸ proposed the following equation for the separation of the polar effect of a substituent into inductive and resonance contributions through a dual parameter treatment of the *ortho*-effect,

$$Q = \alpha\sigma_i + \beta\sigma_R + h \quad (7)$$

where Q is the property being correlated to $\log k$, $\log K$, σ_0 etc.

In a few reactions⁴⁹, the effect of multiple substituents in 3, 4 and 5 positions relative to the reacting side-chain has been observed to be additive since these reaction series obey the Hammett's equation. The effect of multiple substituents can obviously be expressed as the sum of their substituent constants expressed in the form^{50,51},

$$\log k/k^0 = \rho \Sigma \sigma \quad (8)$$

Although this equation is a good approximation, substituents, which interact strongly with each other, must probably be taken out of this generalization.

In compounds which contain substituted phenyl rings with respect to the reaction site (e.g., Ar_1 , Ar_2YZ), the following equation was found to be applicable,

$$\log (k/k^0) = \rho(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) \quad (9)$$

where σ_1 and σ_2 are substituent constants of substituents in Ar_1 and Ar_2 respectively. This equation is valid only if the presence of a substituent in one ring has no effect on the reaction constant for various substituents in the other ring,

For compounds of the type naphthalene skeleton the equation⁵³ used is

$$\log k/KO = n \rho \sigma \quad (10)$$

where n is the number of equally substituted benzene rings.

In solvolysis of polysubstituted benzhydryl chlorides⁵³ it is suggested from the results that the discrepancy in the additivity rule of multiple substituents is most serious when the first substituent is strongly electron-releasing, such as *p*-OCH₃, or electron-attracting such as *m*, *m*-dichloro. It turns out these powerful first substituent influences the reaction constant so much that the influence of the second substituent on reactivity depends on the nature and effect of the first substituent. These results lead to the conclusion that Hammett's equation for multiple substitution in electrophilic side-chain reaction can be represented by an equation of the type,

tion of the type,

$$\log (k/k^0) = \alpha \Sigma \sigma^+ + \beta \quad (11)$$

where α and β are constants characteristic of the principal substituents.

Measurements have been made on a few reaction series of compounds of the type

where R is a substituent in 4- or 5-position relative to the reactive side-chain while x is a constant substituent in 2-position through the series⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶. The effect of multiple substituents for such a system is expressed by a single equation of the type,

$$\log (k/KO) = \sigma \rho + X \quad (12)$$

where X is the effect of substituent ' x ' in the *ortho*-position on the reactivity of unsubstituted compound C_6H_5Y , i. e. $X = \log (k_x/k^0)$. This equation is found to be applicable to nuclear chlorination of benzyl phenyl ethers⁵⁷.

Many reactions of compounds having two or more aromatic rings in equivalent positions relative to the reaction site have also been investigated. In such series when all rings are equally substituted or which involved different substituents on one ring only, no special problems were noticed and the simple Hammett's equation is found to be applicable. For reaction series, which involved a combination of these two situations or those, which had unsymmetrical substitution, Hammett's equation was occasionally applied in the form⁵⁸ of equation (8), where the summation extends over all the substituents in different rings. Literature survey revealed ten reaction series, which followed equation (8). Although large amounts of data could be satisfactorily expressed in terms of equation (8) than the simple equation to compounds in which substituents are present in more than one equivalent ring (equivalent with respect to the reaction centre) or to multiple substituents in one and the same ring, it was found that the precision of representation of this data increased only marginally. This fact shows that a substituent in one ring does not greatly affect the susceptibility of the reaction to the presence of a substituent in another ring. There is no reason to believe that this conclusion should not apply equally to compounds in which several aromatic rings are present in non-equivalent positions relative to the reaction site. Hence, for reactions of such compounds Jaffe⁴⁷ proposed the following equation,

$$\log (k/k^0) = \sigma_1\rho_1 + \sigma_2\rho_2 + \sigma_3\rho_3 + \dots \quad (14)$$

where ρ_1 , ρ_2 etc., measure the susceptibility of the reaction

to the effect of substituents in ring, 1, 2 etc. and σ_1, σ_2 etc. refer to the substituent constants of the substituents present in the respective rings⁴⁷.

It was anticipated that the above equation would also apply to reactions of the type, $A + B \rightarrow$ Products, if both A and B contained a substituted aromatic ring. However, examination of literature revealed several reaction series of this type^{56,60}, which did not obey the above equation even approximately. This was the starting point of the evolution of what is now called Interactive free energy relationships.

Interactive free energy relationships :

For polysubstituted compounds where simultaneous change of substituents in two phenyl rings is possible the additive model of Jaffe⁴⁷ (eqn. 14) which is usually applicable showed most outstanding deviations and these are explained as due to some specific interactions. This shortcoming is in fact a serious amputation of the predictive ability and mechanistic significance of free energy relationships. Miller⁶¹ and later Dubois *et al.*⁶³ proposed an empirical free energy relationship where the non-additivity is taken into account by adding an interaction term to the additive ones. However, this relationship has received few applications, perhaps because a mechanistic significance of the interactive term was not clearly understood at that time.

Later Ruasse and Argile⁶⁷ showed that multiple substituent effects (MSEs) could be analyzed quantitatively in terms of interactive free energy relationships (IFERs) by extending the classical Hammett-Brown relationships established for one substituent. Such treatment for non-additivity restores both the predictive capacity and the mechanistic significance of usual LFER.

Ruasse and Argile successfully applied this equation first to the bromination of polysubstituted α -methylstilbenes⁶⁷. This was later found to be applicable to (i) oxidation of phenyl styryl ketones by Ce^{IV} ⁶⁴, (ii) oxidation of aromatic anils by acid bromate⁶⁵, (iii) Os^{VIII} catalyzed oxidation of phenyl styryl ketones by periodate^{66a}, (iv) oxidation of phenyl styryl ketones by V^V in acid medium^{66b}, (v) Ru^{III} catalyzed oxidation of phenyl styryl ketones by V^V in acid medium^{66c}, (vi) reduction of phenyl styryl ketones using cyclic voltammetry^{66d}, (vii) oxidation of phenyl styryl ketones by pyridinium chlorochromate^{66e} etc.

The additive model of Jaffe⁴⁷ states that the effect of two substituents is the product of each one of them on the unsubstituted compound,

$$\frac{k_{XY}}{k_{HH}} = \frac{k_{XH}}{k_{HH}} \frac{k_{YH}}{k_{HH}} \quad (15)$$

It is readily seen that such an assumption is incorrect. One should write

$$\frac{k_{XY}}{k_{HH}} = \frac{k_{XY}}{k_{XH}} \frac{k_{XH}}{k_{HH}} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{k_{XY}}{k_{HH}} = \frac{k_{XY}}{k_{YH}} \frac{k_{YH}}{k_{HH}} \quad (16)$$

In each ratio only one substituent changes while the other, X, Y, or H remains constant. Consequently, the simple Hammett's relationship holds good. For the tertiary pathway of α -methylstilbene bromination, Ruasse and Argile⁶⁷ suggested the following equation,

$$\log \left(\frac{k_{XY}}{k_{HH}} \right) = \rho_{\beta}^X \sigma_Y + \rho_{\alpha}^H \sigma_x^* \quad \text{or} \quad \rho_{\alpha}^Y \sigma_x^* + \rho_{\beta}^H \sigma_Y \quad (17)$$

Similar type of equation was also suggested by us⁶⁴ for the oxidation of PSK by Ce^{IV} ,

$$\log \left(\frac{k_{XY}}{k_{HH}} \right) = \rho_{Y(X)} \sigma_Y + \rho_{X(Y_0)} \sigma_x$$

or $\rho_{X(Y)} \sigma_x + \rho_{Y(X_0)} \sigma_Y$ (18)

It is possible to get the following equation from the above equations,

$$\frac{\rho_{Y(X)} - \rho_{Y(X_0)}}{\sigma_x} = \frac{\rho_{X(Y)} - \rho_{X(Y_0)}}{\sigma_Y} = q \quad (19)$$

where $\rho_{X(Y_0)}$ and $\rho_{Y(X_0)}$ are reaction constants for substituents in ring X and ring Y respectively with H in the other ring. Similarly, $\rho_{X(Y)}$ and $\rho_{Y(X)}$ are reaction constants for various substituents in these aromatic rings (ring X or Y) respectively for a particular substituent in the other ring; σ_x and σ_Y are Hammett substituent constant for the substituents in these rings, respectively.

This equality must be true whatever may be the substituent X and Y. These ratios are equal to a constant q called the cross-interaction constant. The above equation can be written as

$$\rho_{X(Y)} = \rho_{X(Y_0)} + q \sigma_Y \quad (20a)$$

$$\rho_{Y(X)} = \rho_{Y(X_0)} + q \sigma_X \quad (20b)$$

The free energy relationship that expresses the cumulative effect of X and Y is readily obtained from eqn. (18) by setting $\rho_{X(Y)}$ and $\rho_{Y(X)}$ to their values given by eqn. (20) which is derived from Hammett's formalism. This is

$$\log (k_{XY}/k_{HH}) = \rho_{X(Y_0)} \sigma_Y + \rho_{Y(X_0)} \sigma_X + q \sigma_X \sigma_Y \quad (21)$$

and is termed as interactive free energy relationship. Relationships similar to eqns. (20) and (21) have been established also by Exner⁶⁸ from a statistical point of view and by Palm⁶⁹ and Jenck⁷⁰ from the Taylor expansion of the global effect on reactivity. Thus the reactivity between substituents which leads to a departure from additivity rule, can be expressed quantitatively by the interaction term, equal to the product of a constant q , the cross-interaction constant, with the product of the substituent constants σ_x and σ_y . It follows that substituted reaction system can be accurately defined only, if one knows the reaction constant ρ and the cross-interaction constant q . The value of q can be obtained only through experimental results.

For treating the multiple substituent effects in redox reactions one can consider bromate (BrO_3^-)-aromatic anil reaction as a typical example. Aromatic anils or phenyl styryl ketones (PSKs) have two phenyl rings X and Y on either side of the functional groups.

It is possible to evaluate the reaction constant ρ from the Hammett's plot by varying substituents in one ring X or Y keeping a particular substituent in the other ring constant. It is therefore possible to get several reaction constants for different substituents in one of the two rings for each substituent in the other ring. From such studies it is possible to evaluate the effect of substituents in one ring on the reaction constant ρ obtained by varying the substituents in the other ring. For example in BrO_3^- -anil reaction, the ρ values for various substituents in benzaldehyde moiety are given in Table 3.

Table 3. ρ_x values for various substituents in ring Y

Substituents in aniline moiety (Y) (σ_y)	ρ -Values for substituents in benzaldehyde moiety (ρ_x)	q
$p\text{-OCH}_3$	0.570	0.704
H	0.760	0.000
$m\text{-CH}_3$	0.710	0.714
$p\text{-Cl}$	0.900	0.607
$m\text{-Cl}$	1.04	0.757
$p\text{-NO}_2$	1.30	0.692

From these observations, it is concluded that the magnitude of ρ value for various substituents in ring X is a function of the nature of the substituent in ring Y and vice versa. These results are well-explained by IFER (eqn. 19) given earlier. From eqn. (19) it is clear that a plot of $\rho_{x(y)}$ versus σ_y should be linear if q is constant. Such linear plots have been observed in Ce^{IV} -PSK reaction, Br^{V} -aromatic anil and Os^{VIII} catalyzed oxidation of PSK's by periodate and other

reactions mentioned earlier.

This IFER for the multiple substituent effects accurately describes the substituent effects on the reactivity and regiochemistry. Thus, the general expression not only restores the predictive power of the free energy relationship but also its mechanistic implication. A polysubstituted reaction system is therefore perfectly described only if the reaction constants and the cross-interaction constant q are known. Moreover, q which measures sensitivity of ρ to structural effects can be a valuable source of information regarding the factors which causes ρ to vary.

Oxidation reactions involving trace metal ions as catalysts :

Many transition metal ions such as Ag^{I} , Mn^{II} , Cu^{II} , and complex compounds of several platinum group metals such as Ru^{III} , Rh^{III} , Ru^{VIII} , Os^{VIII} , Ir^{III} etc., catalyze a number of redox process⁷¹⁻⁷³. The catalytic activity is generally attributed to their capacity to (i) exist in more than one oxidation state, (ii) form complexes with organic compounds and (iii) change their coordination number.

A redox reaction, which is otherwise favourable thermodynamically, may still be slow for following reasons : (i) the difficulty in forming a precursor complex between the oxidant and the substrate, (ii) the symmetry prohibition and (iii) slowness of the decomposition of the successor complex formed. Thus substrates like acetic acid, monohydric alcohols which are either not oxidized by certain oxidants or oxidized very slowly under normal conditions, do get oxidized easily in the presence of a catalyst. The way in which the metal ions catalyse these reactions depend on the following factors : (a) the nature of the oxidant employed, (b) the nature of the substrate getting oxidized, (c) the type of metal ion being employed as catalyst and finally (d) the medium employed (acid, alkaline, or neutral).

A metal ion can act as catalyst for a redox process if the following requirements are met : (i) the mean value of the redox potential is around 0.8 to 1.0 V and (ii) the presence of large number of vacant d -orbitals.

The mechanisms of metal ion catalysed redox reactions can be broadly classified into five categories, as discussed below.

Type I mechanism :

where $\text{Ox}^{\text{m}+}$ and $\text{Ox}^{(\text{m}-\text{x})+}$ are the oxidized and reduced forms of the oxidant, $\text{C}^{(\text{n}+\text{x})+}$ and $\text{C}^{\text{n}+}$ the oxidized and re-

duced forms of the catalyst and S is the substrate. This type of catalysis is possible only when the oxidation potential of $C^{n+}/C^{(n+x)+}$ couple is less than that of $Ox^{m+}/Ox^{(m-x)+}$. In general, the rate law for reactions, which follows the above type of mechanism, is

$$\frac{-d[Ox^{m+}]}{dt} = k[Ox^{m+}][S][C^{n+}]$$

The oxidation of Hg_2^{2+} by Ce^{IV} in the presence of Ir^{III} , or Ru^{III} as catalyst⁷¹ are examples of this category. The mechanism suggested is given below.

Type II mechanism :

In this category the catalyst itself preferentially oxidizes the substrate first, probably via a 1 : 1 complex. This happens whenever the oxidation potential of $C^{n+}/C^{(n+x)+}$ is higher than that of $Ox^{m+}/Ox^{(m-x)+}$. The mechanism in such cases can be depicted as

A large number of reactions catalysed by Ru^{III} and Os^{VIII} come under this category. In Ru^{III} catalyzed oxidation of alcohols by periodate in alkaline medium, Rao *et al.*⁷² proposed a similar mechanism involving hydride ion abstraction by Ru^{III} from α -C-H bond of the alcohol. Here the order in [oxidant] is zero.

Type III mechanism :

When the oxidant is unable to reoxidize the reduced form of the catalyst as in the case of chloramine-T (CAT) oxidations⁷³ the following mechanism has been suggested.

These reactions exhibit zero order dependence on [substrate]. This type of mechanism has been observed mainly in Os^{VIII} catalyzed oxidation of some organic compounds by CAT. In the Os^{VIII} catalyzed oxidation of formaldehyde and acetaldehyde by CAT in alkaline medium⁷³, a first order dependence

of rate on [CAT] and $[Os^{VIII}]$ and zero order dependence on [aldehyde] have been explained by a mechanism involving formation of an intermediate complex consisting of one mole of Os^{VIII} and one mole of CAT in the rate-determining step followed by the interaction of this complex with the aldehyde in a fast step to give the products,

The rate law obtained for the above mechanism is

$$\frac{-d[CAT]}{dt} = \frac{k_2 k_3 [CAT][Ox^{VIII}][H_2O]}{k_2 [NaOH]}$$

Type IV mechanism :

In this type, the substrate first forms a complex with the catalyst before it is oxidized by the oxidant to a higher oxidation state complex in a slow step. This complex later disproportionates in a fast step to give the product. The general mechanism proposed is

The Ag^I catalyzed oxidation of carboxylic acids by Ce^{IV} in H_2SO_4 medium⁷⁴ is a typical case belonging to this category. The mechanism proposed is

This type of mechanism was observed when the oxidation

potential of $C^{n+}/C^{(n+x)+}$ was more than that of $Ox^{m+}/Ox^{(m-x)+}$.

Type V mechanism :

Another scheme, which is operative in redox reactions, is when the catalyst acts as good radical trap. Thus,

A typical example is the $Ag^I + Cu^{II}$ catalysed oxidation of acetic acid by Ce^{IV} ⁷⁵,

Transitional metal ions not only alter the rate of redox reactions under homogeneous conditions but also change the mechanism considerably. For instance, oxidation of anilines by Tl^{III} acetate⁷⁶ which follows anionic mechanism changes to a free radical one in the presence of Ru^{III} ions. Based on the kinetic data obtained, the mechanism of oxidation of anilines by Tl^{III} in the absence of Ru^{III} proposed was

The addition of Ru^{III} to Tl^{III} -aniline reaction catalyzes the reaction. Though most of the Ru^{III} -catalyzed oxidations proceed by an ionic mechanism, free radicals have been detected in this particular case. The evidences for the change in mechanism from ionic in the absence of Ru^{III} to free radical pathway in the presence of Ru^{III} are as follows. (i) The Hammett's ρ value for uncatalyzed reaction, which was

-3.0, changed to -0.76 in the presence of Ru^{III} . (ii) Pederson and Martin⁷⁷ reported bromination of toluenes by NBS to follow a radical pathway. The plot of $\log k_2$ (NBS bromination of toluenes) vs $\log k_2$ (Tl^{III} oxidation of anilines) in the presence of Ru^{III} was linear indicating that similar mechanism is operative in both these reactions. (iii) Polymerization was observed when a vinyl monomer was added to the system. (iv) The effect of acid was reversed from one of dependence in the absence of Ru^{III} to being totally independent in the presence of Ru^{III} . In case of uncatalyzed reaction the dependence of rate on [acid] was attributed to the existence of an equilibrium in which Tl^{III} acetate loses an acetate ion. However, this appears to be unimportant in the presence of Ru^{III} as the reaction between Tl^{III} and Ru^{III} is fast leading to the formation of the active species Ru^V . Due to the intervention of oxidation step involving inorganic ion hydrolysis equilibrium is of no significance and this results in independence of rate on [acid]. While the rate showed first order dependence on $[Tl^{III}]$ and $[S]$ in the presence as well as absence of Ru^{III} , the catalyzed one showed first order dependence on $[Ru^{III}]$ also. In view of this, the following mechanism has been suggested.

The rate law obtained for the above mechanism is

$$\frac{-d[Tl^{III}]}{dt} = k[Tl^{III}][Ru^{III}][\text{aniline}]$$

In the above mechanism, the catalysis is attributed to the formation of a reactive Ru^V species by the $Ru^{III} + Tl^{III}$ reaction. However, Ru^{III} and also Os^{VIII} are known to catalyze an oxidation reaction involving organic compounds by direct electron transfer from the substrate in a slow step to give the product. The reduced form of the catalyst gets reoxidized by the oxidant in a fast step. In such reactions, the observed catalysis is due to continuous regeneration of the catalyst in a fast reaction by the oxidant since the oxidant concentration is several times greater than the concentration of catalyst. This type of mechanism has been proposed by several workers during their study on Ru^{III}/Os^{VIII} catalyzed oxidation of organic compounds by HCF, periodate, bromate, Cu^{III} , Ag^{III} etc.^{72,78-81}. Ru^{III} catalyzed oxidation of alcohols by bromate is a typical example of this type. Radhakrishnamurthi and Sarangi⁷⁸ who observed a first order dependence of rate on $[S]$ and $[Ru^{III}]$ and zero order dependence on $[BrO_3^-]$, suggested an outersphere complex between Ru^{III} and

alcohol based on the clean first order dependence of rate on [S] and linear plot of $1/k$ vs $1/[S]$ passing through the origin. A high negative ρ value of -4.21 indicated hydride ion transfer mechanism to be operative. The following mechanism has been suggested.

The rate law derived was

$$\frac{-d[\text{Br}^{\text{V}}]}{dt} = k[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}][\text{S}]$$

In $\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}$ catalyzed oxidations following this type of mechanism, it is not always necessary that the reaction should proceed by a hydride ion transfer mechanism. For instance during the Os^{VIII} catalyzed oxidation of some unsaturated acids by periodate⁸², OsO_4 attacks the double bond to give the hydroxylated product first which later gives the final products. The mechanism proposed was as shown below.

The rate law derived was

$$-d[\text{IO}_4^-]/dt = k_1 k_2 [\text{S}][\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] / (k_{-1} + k_2 + k_1 [\text{S}])$$

Another interesting aspect of metal ion catalysis is when the oxidant is unable to reoxidize the reduced form of the catalyst as in the case of chloramine-T oxidations. Here the catalyst itself forms a complex with the oxidant (CAT) preferentially in a slow step, which then reacts with the sub-

strate in a fast step. The catalysis is attributed to the high reactivity of the complex formed between CAT and Os^{VIII} compared to the original oxidant, viz. CAT. In the Os^{VIII} catalyzed oxidation of formaldehyde and acetaldehyde by CAT in alkaline medium, the first order dependence of rate on $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ and $[\text{CAT}]$ and zero order dependence on [aldehyde] indicated formation of an intermediate species involving one mole of Os^{VIII} and one mole of CAT.

The rate law obtained for the above mechanism is

$$\frac{-d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = \frac{k_2 k_3 [\text{CAT}][\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{k_2 [\text{NaOH}]}$$

A similar type of mechanism was found to be operative in Os^{VIII} catalyzed oxidation of α -hydroxy acids⁷³, benzaldehydes⁸³ etc. by CAT in alkaline medium. In the Os^{VIII} catalyzed oxidation of benzaldehydes by CAT the complete absence of substituent effect supports the above mechanism.

In all cases where the catalyst first oxidizes the substrate and the role of the oxidant is only to regenerate the catalyst, the rates and activation parameters should be same irrespective of the oxidant used. Indeed in a recent study we have been able to show that this indeed is so in the Os^{VIII} catalyzed oxidation of 2-propanol by diperiodatocuprate(III) {DPC}, periodate, hexacyanoferrate (HCF) and chloramine-T (CAT) (Table 4).

During the oxidation of 2-propanol by OsO_4 , the order in [S] and $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ was found to be unity each. The rate was found to increase with increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$. No evidence was found for free radicals as well as for complex formation. Based on the above information a mechanism similar to that of Os^{VIII} -catalyzed oxidation of 2-propanol by HCF or periodate or DPC was proposed.

The rate law is

$$-\frac{d \ln[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]}{dt} = k'_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k K_1 K_2 [2\text{-Propanol}][\text{OH}^-]}{1 + K_1 [\text{OH}^-]}$$

Table 4

Reaction	$10^2 \times \text{initial rate} / [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	Order in		
			[2-Propanol]	[Os ^{VIII}]	[Oxidant]
Propanol + Os ^{VIII}	1.68	63.7	1.0	1.0	-
2-Propanol + Os ^{VIII} + DPC	1.31	65.0	1.0	1.0	zero
2-Propanol + Os ^{VIII} + HCF	1.28	63.7	1.0	1.0	zero
2-Propanol + Os ^{VIII} + IO ₄ ⁻	1.30	60.2	1.0	1.0	zero
2-Propanol + Os ^{VIII} + CAT	0.46	34.3	zero	1.0	1.0

The rate and other kinetic features observed for Os^{VIII}-catalyzed oxidation of 2-propanol by CAT was however not the same as that obtained with other oxidants suggesting a different mechanism to be operative.

The use of mixture of two metal ions as homogeneous catalysts in redox reactions is of recent interest. It is reported that the rate of oxidation of a substrate in the presence of a mixture of two metal ions is greater than the algebraic sum of the rates of oxidation of the substrate when the two metal ions are taken separately. Some of the reactions that have been studied and the rate constants reported are listed below.

In the example of Table 5 the concentration of the catalyst (metal ions) is of the order of 10⁻³ M. However, some metal ions like Os^{VIII} and Ru^{III} are known to exhibit catalytic activity in the concentration range of 10⁻⁶ to 10⁻⁷ M. The catalytic activity of Ru^{III} + Os^{III} mixture was also reported to be higher than the sum of the individual catalytic rate constants⁸⁵.

In the example of Table 6, the order in [Os^{VIII}] at constant [Ru^{III}], and [Ru^{III}] at constant [Os^{VIII}] were found to be one each. The order in [periodate] and that in [2-propanol] were zero and fractional, respectively. Since Ru^{III} is known to be a better catalyst and hence, a better hydride ion abstractor than Os^{VIII}, a mechanism in which Os^{VIII} first forms a complex with 2-propanol from which a hydride ion (in-

Table 5. Oxidation of 2-propanol by Ce^{IV} in the presence of various catalysts⁸⁴

[Ce^{IV}] = 4 × 10⁻³ M, [Ag⁺] = [Mn²⁺] = [Ag⁺ + Mn²⁺] = 0.002 M
Temp. = 323 K

Catalyst	[Ag ⁺]	[Mn ²⁺]	[Ag ⁺] + [Mn ²⁺]
$k'' \times 10^5$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	6.12	10.2	18.9

stead getting transferred to Os^{VIII} as in Os^{VIII} catalysed reaction) is transferred to Ru^{III} in the rate-determining step is proposed to explain the results. An approximately similar mechanism has been proposed by Kemp and Waters⁸⁶ in the oxidation of formic acid by Mn^{III} where an electron is picked up by Mn^{III} from HCOO-Mn^{IV} complex.

Table 6. Periodate oxidation of 2-propanol in the presence of Ru^{III}, Os^{VIII} and Ru^{III} + Os^{VIII}

[Periodate] = 2.00 × 10⁻³ M, [OH⁻] = 4.00 × 10⁻³ M; Temp = 303 K

Catalyst	Os ^{VIII}	Ru ^{III}	Os ^{VIII} + Ru ^{III}
$k'' \times 10^{-3}$ dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	1.58	11.6	41.6
E^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	25.2	18.2	12.7

The enhanced rate in the case of Ru^{III} + Os^{VIII} mixture catalyzed oxidation compared to when a single metal ion is used as a catalyst can be explained by comparing the activated complexes formed in the two cases. In the case of mixture catalysed oxidation, the loss of hydrogen as hydride ion appears to be more facile as it is coming from the hydroxylated Os^{VIII}-alcohol complex to Ru^{III} and not from the alcohol moiety directly as in the case of Ru^{III}-catalyzed reaction⁸⁵

Co-oxidation :

An oxidation reaction that proceeds at a faster rate when the reaction is carried out in the presence of a mixture of two substrates compared to the sum of the rates at which the two substrates undergo the oxidation individually with the same oxidant under the same conditions has been shown

by Hassan and Rocek to involve transfer of more than two electrons from both the substrates in a single step and they termed such reactions as co-oxidation reactions. Interest in these reactions has been of recent origin. The first such reaction involving multi-electron transfer with 2-propanol and oxalic acid as substrates and chromic acid as the oxidant was reported by Hassan and Rocek⁸⁷. Ever since this co-oxidation reaction was reported in 1972, many new systems involving mono- and bifunctional organic substrates with various oxidants like Cr^{VI} 88-95, IO₄⁻ (Refs. 96, 97), BrO₃⁻ (Ref. 98) etc., have been investigated. The unique feature of all these co-oxidation reactions is that a direct multi-electron transfer can be effected in a single step from the substrates to the oxidant. This offers a subject for further investigation from a mechanistic point of view. Also this offers a field to try out new systems that mimic biological systems where multi-electron transfer reactions are known to occur although the exact mode of electron transfer and the role of electron carriers is not well understood even today. Cr^{VI} oxidation of oxalic acid has been investigated by many workers. Chakravarty and Ghosh⁹⁹ reported first order dependence on [Cr^{VI}], second and third order in [oxalic acid], with complex dependence on acidity. Bakore and Jain¹⁰⁰ were the first to report that a much simpler rate dependence on [oxalic acid] can be obtained if instead of total concentration of oxalic acid, the concentration of the undissociated oxalic acid and mono-oxalate anion are used. Hassan and Rocek⁸⁷ after a detailed study of the oxalic acid oxidation by Cr^{VI} over wide range of concentrations of oxalic acid, Cr^{VI}, H⁺ etc., concluded that at concentrations of oxalic acid in the range 10⁻²-10⁻¹ M, the second order term in oxalic acid becomes prominent compared to the first order one and hence, proposed that oxalic acid in the form of anion first forms a 1 : 2 complex with Cr^{VI}, before it is oxidized. During this process Cr^{VI} is converted to Cr^{III}. An organic substrate generally undergoes atmost a two-electron oxidation in a single step. A one-step three-electron reduction of an oxidant must therefore involve more than one molecule of the organic substrate in the activated complex and the rate law must show a higher order than one in the total concentration of organic substrate involved. Since the order in [oxalic acid] was 2.0, it was assumed that the 1 : 2 complex of Cr^{VI} undergoes a 3e⁻ reduction.

As mentioned earlier Hassan and Rocek⁸⁷ were the first to report the interesting observation of rate acceleration when 2-propanol was added to oxalic acid-Cr^{VI} system which they referred to as co-oxidation of the mixture of oxalic acid (OxH₂) and 2-propanol (IPA). The rate of co-oxidation was found to be first order in each of the reactants, i.e. [2-

propanol], [OxH₂], and [Cr^{VI}]. The overall reaction is represented as

The three-electron reduction of Cr^{VI} to Cr^{III} could be attained by a one-equivalent oxidation of 2-propanol and two-equivalent oxidation of oxalic acid as given in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Stoichiometric equation :

An alternative path available for Cr^{VI} reduction to Cr^{III} is by a two-equivalent oxidation of oxalic acid and one-equivalent oxidation of 2-propanol as given in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

Stoichiometric equation :

Schemes 1 and 2 represent imaginary mechanisms which require to be substantiated with suitable evidences. If Scheme 1 is operative, the ratio of acetone : CO₂ would be 1 : 4. Scheme 2 on the other hand envisages acetone : CO₂ ratio to be 1 : 1. The observed stoichiometry, however varied between 1 : 1.5 and 2 : 2, which is not compatible with either of the two values expected as per the above schemes.

Some of the important observations that helped in understanding what is happening in these reactions are as follows. (1) The yield of acetone did not decrease (on the contrary the ratio acetone : CO₂ increased) in the presence of a free radical scavenger. This shows that acetone is formed in a two-electron oxidation and not via a free radical path. (2) Acetone : CO₂ ratio changed from 1 : 1.5-1 : 2.2 in the absence of scavenger to 1 : 1 in the presence of scavenger. Any proposed mechanism should therefore be able to explain not only the formation of the transition state involving one molecule each of the two substrates and Cr^{VI}, but also the products obtained, and the stoichiometry observed in the presence and absence of a free radical scavenger. Taking

into account the ability of chromic acid to form a stable 1 : 1 cyclic complex with oxalic acid and the observed stoichiometry, a mechanism involving formation of an ester type intermediate between Cr^{VI} and (COOH)₂ that combines with 2-propanol to give a ternary complex has been proposed. This ternary complex is believed to decompose by a direct 3-electron transfer from the two substrates to the oxidant in a rate-limiting step (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3. Cr^{VI} oxidation of isopropanol in the presence of oxalic acid

Cr^V can react with (COOH)₂ or (CH₃)₂CHOH.

(1) If all Cr^V reacted with (COOH)₂, then
(COOH)₂ + Cr^V → Cr^{III} + 2 CO₂ + H₂O

Stoichiometry :

Acetone : CO₂ = 1 : 4.

(2) If all the Cr^V reacted with (CH₃)₂CHOH, then
(CH₃)₂CHOH + Cr^V → Cr^{III} + (CH₃)₂C=O + H₂O

In the absence of a scavenger, the CO₂^{•-} may undergo further oxidation, resulting in higher yields of CO₂ or the COOH radicals may dimerize to give oxalic acid.

2 COOH → (COOH)₂ or disproportionate to give CO₂ and HCOOH

This explains the higher yield of CO₂ in the absence of a radical scavenger. This also explains the 1 : 1 yield of CO₂ : acetone in the presence of a scavenger wherein the CO₂^{•-} is completely eliminated by the radical scavenger.

If the oxidation of a single substrate, let us say, 2-propanol is considered then this leads to the formation of an

unstable and very reactive Cr^V species¹⁰¹ which has to get reduced to the stable Cr^{III} species by a reaction with another molecule of the substrate in a separate step. The reaction is therefore expected to be greatly facilitated if Cr^{VI} could be reduced directly to Cr^{III}, thus avoiding the formation of energetically unfavourable Cr^V species. The ternary system is thus believed to offer a more convenient way for Cr^{VI} to move over to Cr^{III} and hence, the increased reactivity of the co-oxidation reaction compared to the reactions involving the individual substrates. Thus the proposed mechanism of co-oxidation of oxalic acid and 2-propanol by Cr^{VI} envisages a 3-electron transfer with simultaneous breaking of C–H and C–C bonds in the rate-limiting step. The proof for the C–H bond cleavage comes from the observed deuterium isotope effect studies with 2-deutero-2-propanol, *k_H*/*k_D* = 5.9 (Ref. 87b). In a subsequent communication Ramesh and Rocek¹⁰² demonstrated the C–C bond cleavage (of OxH₂) from a study of the ¹³C isotope effect. By measuring the mass ratios of ¹²CO₂ and ¹³CO₂ on a mass spectrometer a significant carbon isotope effect *k¹²*/*k¹³* = 1.025 was obtained which gave the unambiguous evidence for C–C bond cleavage in the transition state of the rate-limiting step of the co-oxidation reaction (step-3 of Scheme 3). The mechanism suggests that two C–H bonds are broken in the rate-determining step. Evidence for such a direct three electron transfer comes from the kinetic isotope effect studies.

Scheme 4. Cr^{VI} + isopropanol + glycolic acid system.

If the co-oxidation reaction involved two consecutive steps, a one-electron step followed by a two-electron transfer step, or a two-electron oxidation step followed by a one-electron step then, one of them would be rate-determining and the kinetic isotope effect of the co-oxidation reaction is

expected to give a value similar to that observed in the oxidation of one of these substrates. On the contrary, if a direct three-electron transfer occurred in the rate-determining step (as shown in Scheme 4), then one may expect an enormous isotope effect. As expected a very large isotope effect, $k_H/k_D = 34.4$ was observed for the co-oxidation reaction of glycolic acid and 2-propanol. The observed kinetic isotope effects for the oxidation of glycolic acid and 2-propanol when taken individually are 6.0 and 5.8, respectively, supporting the co-oxidation scheme represented in Scheme 4, where C-H bond of glycolic acid and C-H bond of 2-propanol are shown to undergo fission in the transition state.

Acknowledgement

The author wishes to express his deep sense of gratitude to all his teachers particularly, Late Prof. Y. Vishwanatham (S. V. University), Late Prof. S. S. Muhammad (Osmania), Prof. M. Santappa (Madras), Prof. T. Navaneeth Rao (Osmania), Prof. D. Schulte Froelande and Dr. E. Bothe (Max Plank Institute for Strahlen Chemie, Germany). He is grateful to his senior colleagues in the research field Prof. Y. K. Gupta (Rajasthan), Prof. N. Venkatasubramanian (Madras), Prof. P. S. Radhakrishnamurthy (Berhampur) for their help in different ways, inspiration and encouragement. He wishes to place on record the excellent work done by all his 50 odd research scholars during their Ph.D. program under his supervision. He is thankful to Department of Science and Technology (New Delhi) for its financial assistance, which helped to compile all the work, presented in this article. He is also grateful to the U.G.C. (New Delhi) for generous financial assistance at different times, which enabled him to get useful data in this field of work.

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